

Global Health Security

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Citation: *Anas Malik Radif Alubaidi. Global Health Security. Ann Med Res Pub Health. 2024;2(1):1-2.*

Received Date: 28 December, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 02 January, 2024; **Published Date:** 02 January, 2024

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ABSTRACT

The increase in both the international travels and the international trades, population growth, population movement, ecological changes, and both insufficient and inadequate attention to the already existing weak incapable healthcare systems in parts of the world, all are the key drivers for the risk of infectious diseases threats and for the emergence of such threats. Such challengeable risks need to be addressed properly and then to be limited appropriately by global coordination and worldwide collaboration to achieve a level of health security that would ensure and provide both the prevention and the control that are needed, and that health security is known as the Global Health Security (Office of Global Affairs (OGA), 2023).

KEYWORDS

Global Health Security

DISCUSSION

Global health security per United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and per Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) is defined as the existence of strong and resilient public health systems that can and able to prevent, detect, and respond to infectious disease threats, wherever they occur globally (CDC, 2022).

Top global health security risks might include Emergence and spread of new infectious diseases, Ever-increasing globalization of travel and trade, enabling disease to spread, Rise of drug-resistant, disease-causing pathogens, and Potential for accidental release, theft or illicit use of dangerous pathogens (CDC, 2022).

Per CDC, the four core areas to fight top global health security risks are Surveillance systems, Laboratory networks to accurately diagnose diseases and identify new pathogens, Workforce development of frontline staff to identify, track, and contain outbreaks at their source, and Emergency Management systems to coordinate response efforts when crises occur (CDC, 2022).

Per World Health Organization (WHO), Global public health security is defined as the activities required, both proactive and reactive, to minimize and limit both the danger and the impact of acute public health events that endanger population's health across geographical regions and international boundaries (WHO, 2023).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Global Health Security focuses and works on prevention and detection by anticipating and preventing any potential risks for outbreaks, on health emergency preparedness, on response and coordination toward any outbreak, and on global health partnerships. The implementation and the application of each one of these perspectives and actions would be globally worldwide. Now, to achieve the Global Health Security in order to have the better outcomes possible then the global health challenges need to be addressed, limited and then controlled by close coordination and structured collaboration with a wide array of stakeholders from around the world to align efforts and to find resolutions (Office of Global Affairs (OGA), 2023).

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